

Phonological Challenges in the Recitation of Al-Fātiḥah among Nigerian Muslims

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ABSTRACT

Background: Among some Nigerian Muslims, there exists a belief that the correct recitation of Arabic texts—particularly with accurate articulation of the makhārij al-ḥurūf (points of articulation)—is nearly impossible, due to the perception of Arabic as a difficult foreign language. Such an assumption, however, stands in contrast to the Islamic spirit of ta'lim (teaching) and ta'allum (learning), as well as the profound influence of Arabic on the cultural, social, and religious life of Muslims.

Objectives: This study seeks to examine the misconception regarding the difficulty of mastering Arabic pronunciation among Nigerian Muslims. It further explores the centrality of Arabic in Muslim life—intellectually, morally, socially, and spiritually—especially in relation to the recitation of the Qur'ān.

Methodology: The research adopts historical, descriptive, and analytical approaches. Particular attention is given to Sūrat al-Fātiḥah, the opening chapter of the Qur'ān, to highlight the phonological challenges faced by some Nigerian Muslims in its recitation.

Findings: The study reveals that Arabic is not unique in being a foreign language within Nigeria. Nigerian Muslims also learn English and French, often attaining proficiency in speech, reading, and communication. The presumption that Arabic cannot be mastered is therefore unfounded.

Conclusion: The relationship between Muslims and the Arabic language is vital for intellectual development, moral refinement, social cohesion, and religious devotion. Overcoming phonological obstacles in Qur'ānic recitation—particularly in Sūrat al-Fātiḥah, which is recited in every unit of the Muslim prayer—will enhance Qur'ānic literacy and strengthen the role of Arabic in the lives of Nigerian Muslims.

KEYWORDS: Phonological Challenges – Nigeria – Qur'ānic Recitation – Sūrat Al-Fātiḥah – Islamic Linguistic Studies

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INTRODUCTION

Before the 7th century, scholars in the African region would hold teaching circles and gatherings in which they instructed boys and young students in the Arabic alphabet and the recitation of the Qur'ān, following a traditional method of transmission. Within these sessions, they also taught basic principles of prayer and worship. Among the most widely used references for teaching prayer and acts of devotion among the Nigerian Muslim community were al-Akhdarī, al-'Ashmāwī, al-Qurṭubī, and Mukhtaṣar al-Khalīl, all foundational texts in the Mālikī school of law. Some later scholars also relied on the textbook al-Durūs al-Awwaliyyah, which was common in Qur'ānic schools, study circles, and local institutions.

The traditional method adopted by scholars for teaching children the Arabic alphabet, however, produced an unintended effect: it left a marked influence on the phonetic patterns of learners, shaping their pronunciation and transmitting these habits from one generation to another. While this system was originally seen as praiseworthy, the situation began to change in the late 1990s, with the return of students and delegations who had studied in Arab countries such as Egypt, Libya, Saudi Arabia, and others.

Nevertheless, the phonetic imprint of earlier methods still poses an obstacle to the correct recitation of al-Fātiḥah among many Muslims in Nigeria. It is on this basis that this paper examines these **phonological challenges** through a linguistic and analytical approach, drawing upon both classical and modern linguistic insights. The paper will be structured as follows:

1. An overview of phonological studies in Nigeria.
2. The theory of lahn (phonetic error) in the science of Qur'ānic recitation.
3. Phonological challenges as discussed by linguists.
4. Case studies of phonological challenges in the recitation of al-Fāṭihah in Nigeria.
5. Conclusion.
6. References.

History of Arabic Phonological Studies in Nigeria

The Stage of Origin

The beginnings of phonetic and phonological study in Nigerian linguistic research can be traced back to the **pre-colonial era**, rooted in the study of **tajwīd** (the science of Qur'ānic recitation), one of the earliest Islamic sciences introduced by devoted scholars—since tajwīd accompanies the Qur'ān itself.

By the **eighteenth century**, intellectual production expanded across different disciplines under the leadership of the **Fodian scholars** (the movement led by Shaykh 'Uthmān dan Fodio and his companions). Their contributions granted them a lasting intellectual distinction over other West African kingdoms that participated in shaping the region's civilization.

Yet, from the very beginning of Arabic's spread in West Africa, **phonological challenges emerged**, especially among non-Arab populations who learned Arabic as a **second language (L2)**. Learners quickly realized that certain Arabic sounds did not exist in their native tongues, and thus attempted to substitute them with phonetically similar sounds.

The first to recognize and address this linguistic phenomenon in a corrective manner was **Uthmān Bn Fodio**. He observed errors in the prayers, supplications, and Qur'ānic recitations of the people, noting mistakes in the articulation of Arabic letters and in the distinction between short and long vowels.

Deremie comments on this phenomenon in his discussion of the contact between Arabic and Yoruba, citing an old report attributed to bn Fodio people would lengthen the vowel in Allāhu Akbar, pronouncing it as (الله أكبر) Allāhu Akbāar instead. This subtle change transformed the meaning in the context of the (adhān) Muslim call to solah and iqāmah, producing unintended connotations. (Deremi, pg 96)

Another towering figure of this era was 'Abdullāh ibn Fodio, recognized as a pioneer of rhetorical and linguistic thought in eighteenth-century West Africa. His intellectual influence spread beyond Nigeria to other parts of the region and beyond. Researchers have documented his contributions to grammar, morphology, rhetoric, prosody, literature, Qur'ānic sciences, and other fields.

Agaka describes 'Abdullāh ibn Fodio as a leading literary thinker, noting that his attention to phonological aesthetics was part of his refined taste, which demanded strength and intensity in some contexts, and delicacy and softness in others. His use of rhyme and sound patterns in poetry often evoked profound meanings and reinforced the lofty objectives of his compositions. It is therefore not surprising that he stood out among his contemporaries in recognizing and applying phonological principles, benefiting from resources such as al-Qāmūs al-Muḥīṭ, one of the most prominent dictionaries of his time. (Agaka, p.46)

Thus, phonetic and phonological studies in Nigeria originated in the eighteenth century among scholars and literati, developing in a manner similar to other scientific disciplines in their formative stages.

The Stage of Growth

The **nineteenth century** witnessed continuous intellectual and cultural development in West Africa in general, and in Nigeria in particular. This growth was nurtured by two major influences: the cultural legacy planted by the **Fodians** in the eighteenth century, and the arrival of **European colonial powers** with another phase of foreign civilizations and educational structures. Inspired by a strong cultural identity, scholars continued the legacy of their predecessors, making Arabic language and culture central to their educational mission, thus, established centers of learning across Nigeria, leading a cultural revival from both the north and south.

In the north figures included **Wazir Junaid, Muḥammad al-Bukhārī**. (Ali, p.43) and the likes, while in the west **Muḥammad Bīgūrī, Jāmi' al-adaBī (known as Tāj al-Adab)**—author of (Kitāb al-Shughrub in lexicography) **Kamāl al-Dīn al-Adabī, Ādam ibn 'Abdullāh al-Ilūrī**, and others in the twentieth century further strengthened the efforts in Arabic literacy through academic exchanges between Nigeria and advanced Arab countries. Evidence of these exchanges remain visible: in the south, institutions such as the University of Ibadan, Ilorin, and Lagos, as well as Islamic institutes in Ibadan; and in the north, the influence of Sudanese scholars at Bayero University in Kano, Usmanu Danfodiyo University in Sokoto, Ahmad Bello University, in Zaria and University of Maiduguri in Borno, before this stage, Arabic education was primarily conducted at two levels: **Qur'ānic schools (katatib)** and **scholarly institutes (ṣuwārī al-'ulamā')**. (Agaka, p.14)

Deremie classified the levels of Arabic phonological acquisition among Nigerian learners, assessing their articulation, segmentation, and reading of Arabic letters. He quantified the outcome at **12.5 points**, describing the substitutions made by Hausa and Yoruba learners, including their use of **transliteration** strategies. (Deremi, p.96)

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Arabic Transliteration الاتحاد الحرفي	Hausa Pronunciation النطق الهوساوي	Yoruba Pronunciation النطق اليورباوي
أ alif	alefu or aluu	Aleefu
ب ba'	ba	Baa
ت ta'	ta	Taa
ث tha'	Cha	Sa
ج jim	Jim	Jiimu
ح ha'	ha karami	Akarimi
خ kha'	ha-mairuwa	Aamairuwa
د dal	dali	Dali
ذ zhal	zali	Sali
ر rha'	ra	Raa
ز za'	zaira	Sinra
س sin	sin	Sin
ش shin	Shin mai ruwa	Shinmiruwa
ص sad	sadi	Sodi
ض dod	radi	Lodi
ط ta'	da mai hannu	Tamisonnu
ظ za'	za mai hannu	Samisonu
ع ayn	an bakin wofin	Ambakofi
غ ghayn	ga bakin wofin	Ganbakinwofi
ف fa'	fa guje	Fagunje
ق qaf	ka mai ruwa	kamairuwa
ك kaf	kan lansa	Kanulasa
ل lam	lam'ara	Lamuara
م mim	mi'ara	Miara
ن nun	nu'ara	Nuara

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هـ ha'	ha babba	Habuba
و wa'	wau	Wo
ل lamalif	lamaluu	Lamolfeefu
ء hamzah		Alansa
ي ya'	ya'ara	Yaara

Analysis of these findings shows that Yoruba learners largely acquired their pronunciation from Hausa speakers. Both communities, however, underwent significant phonological shifts:

- هـ → s / sh
- خ → ḥ
- ذ → s
- ز → s
- ص → s (approximate)
- ض → r (Hausa) / l (Yoruba and Hausa)
- ط → d / t
- ظ → s (Yoruba)
- ع → a
- ق → k
- هـ → ḥ
- hamzah (ء) → ḥ

A detailed discussion of these phonological transformations, their challenges, and their impact on Nigeria's Arabic linguistic environment will follow in the third section of this paper.

The Stage of Flourishing

In the late twentieth century, phonological studies in Nigeria had matured significantly, evolving from a purely intuitive appreciation into a field of theoretical, analytical, and systematic inquiry. This development was propelled by prominent academics through linguistic research, seminars, conferences, and workshops, and became institutionalized within university curricula.

Phonology was taught at various academic levels of undergraduates, Masters, and PhD as well as in specialized institutions such as Colleges of Education, Faculties of Arabic and Islamic Studies, and other higher institutes offering Arabic language and literature. A defining feature of this flourishing stage was the emergence of renowned Qur'ānic reciters, each with distinctive phonetic styles (ṣawtiyyāt) used in preaching and public recitation. Among the most famous were:

In the north:

- Sheikh Mahmud Gummi
In the west
- The late **Shaykh Kamāl al-Dīn al-Adabī**, whose unique style was called "**al-ṣawtiyyah al-adabiyyah**", linked to his cultural institution.
- The late **Allāmah Ādam 'Abdullāh al-Ilūrī**, associated with "**al-ṣawtiyyah al-markaziyyah**", tied to his educational and cultural center.

The Theory of (Laḥn) Phonetic Solecism in the Science of Qur'ānic Recitation

The scholars of Qur'ānic recitation ('ilm al-qirā'āt) and classical linguists devoted great attention to the precise study of the valid modes of Qur'ānic recitation, safeguarding their chains of transmission as received from the Prophet ﷺ. Al-Qaṣṣālānī defines qirā'āt as: "The science by which one comes to know the points of agreement and difference among the reciters regarding language, inflection, elision and affirmation, separation and connection, as transmitted. (Al-buraidi, p.3)

Al-Qāḍī, in his book al-Budūr al-Zāhira, defines it as:

"A science through which the manner of pronouncing the Qur'ānic words is known, as well as the way of their performance, whether in agreement or difference, with each variant traced back to its transmitter. (Al-Buraidi, p.3)

The Qur'an Linguists classified the modes of reciting the Qur'ān into three levels:

1. **Taḥqīq (deliberate recitation)**: slow and measured recitation, with calmness and composure, giving each letter its due articulation and qualities.

2. **Ḥadr (rapid recitation):** quicker recitation, yet while still observing the rules of tajwīd.

3. **Tadwīr (moderate recitation):** an intermediate mode between taḥqīq and ḥadr.

The Linguists considered tartīl (beautiful, well-measured recitation) to be a general term encompassing all three modes. When it comes to (laḥn) phonetic error, the scholars of Qur’ānic recitation classified it into two categories:

- **Soft hidden Error (laḥn khafī):** A subtle mistake affecting the conventional rules of recitation without changing the meaning. i.e omitting nasalization (ghunnah), lengthening a short vowel, or shortening a long vowel. These are all referred “soft” because only trained reciters are able to detect it. The ruling on such errors varies between being makrūh (disliked) and ḥarām (forbidden).
- **Obvious Error (laḥn jaliyy):** A clear mistake that distorts the meaning of the Qur’ān, such as replacing the letter tā’ (ط) with dāl (د), pronouncing an ‘amta with a ḍammah on the tā’ (making it an ‘amtu), or replacing one letter with another—for example, saying allazī (الَّذِي) instead of alladhī (اللَّهِ). It is called “obvious” because it is recognizable to both specialists and non-specialists. Such errors are unanimously considered ḥarām and a grave sin

It is clear that reciting the Qur’ān with a letter outside the seven canonical (mutawātir) readings is categorically impermissible. Some scholars even declared anyone who deliberately did so to be guilty of disbelief.

The classical Linguists of recitation strongly refuted the claim of Muḥammad ibn al-Ḥasan ibn Muqsim al-Baghdādī—the grammarian and Qur’ān reciter—who asserted:

“Any reading that conforms to Arabic grammar and the script of the (muṣḥaf), even if it has no chain of transmission, is permissible.” Abū Ṭāhir ibn Abī Ḥāshim commented on this, saying:

“A man in our time arose, claiming that any form of Arabic expression that accords with the muṣḥaf can be considered a valid recitation in prayer and elsewhere. By this he introduced an innovation that deviated from the straight path. A council was convened in Baghdad to examine this matter, attended by jurists and Qur’ān Linguistic expert, who unanimously forbade it. The man was punished, compelled to repent, and a legal record was written against him. (Al-buraidi. ibid)

Phonological Challenges According to Linguists

A significant number of specialists and researchers in linguistics and phonetics from this region—such as Abū Bakr, ‘Abd al-Raḥīm, Hārūn, Ogunbiyi, Akorede, and Ologele—have attempted to identify for scholars the Arabic consonants that are most difficult for non-native speakers in Nigeria to pronounce correctly.

Their findings are as follows:

- **For Hausa speakers,** ten consonants are critically difficult: /f/, /q/, /t/, /z/, /th/ (ث), /dh/ (ذ), /s/, /d/, /l/, /gh/.
- **For Yoruba speakers,** eleven consonants are considered difficult: /t/, /d/, /q/, /l/, /th/ (ث), /dh/ (ذ), /z/, /z/, /s/, /kh/, /gh/.
- **For Igbo speakers,** the challenging sounds are: /t/, /th/ (ث), /h/, /kh/, /d/, /s/, /q/, /dh/ (ذ).
- **For Nupe speakers,** the difficult sounds are: /kh/, /h/, /th/ (ث), /d/, /s/, /z/.

In addition to these, cultural exchange and dialectal influences among the Yoruba people have added **two further consonants** to their list of problematic sounds: /s/ and /sh/.

- In some Yoruba-speaking areas such as **Lagos and Ijebu-Ode**, speakers often pronounce the letter /s/ as /sh/. For example, in reciting the Qur’ānic verse wa-sh-shamsu (“By the sun”), they pronounce both instances as /sh/: wash-shamsh. This tendency arises from the local perception that educated Lagos speakers frequently overuse /sh/ in their speech.
- Conversely, in Yoruba-speaking regions such as **Ibadan, Ilorin, Owo, Oyo, Ayede**, and stretching to parts of **Offa and Osun State**, the opposite occurs: the letter /sh/ is pronounced as /s/. Thus, the verse wa-sh-shamsu is recited as wassamsu. This variation is explained as a result of local dialectal influence.

These phonological challenges were scientifically analyzed by Ḥamzah when he stated “Students of Arabic from the Yoruba and Hausa communities find it difficult to pronounce **interdental sounds** (such as /th/, /dh/), some **pharyngeal sounds** (such as /h/, /l/), and **emphatic consonants** (such as /s/, /d/, /t/, /z/). However, both Hausa and Yoruba speakers do not face difficulties with the Arabic **vowel sounds (ḥarakāt)**, since these already exist in their native languages.” (Hamzah, p. 69-70)

If we gather the findings of Nigerian phoneticians regarding the Arabic consonants that are most difficult for Nigerians to pronounce correctly: alongside the sounds which these Arabic consonants are usually substituted, as noted earlier by Deremi, it will appear that Hausa, Yoruba, Igbo, and Nupe speakers share most of these difficulties.

For example:

- **Hausa:** /th/ (ث), /dh/ (ذ), /s/ (ص), /d/ (ض), /t/ (ط), /z/ (ظ), /l/ (ع), /gh/ (غ), /f/ (ف), /q/ (ق).
- **Yoruba:** /th/ (ث), /kh/ (خ), /dh/ (ذ), /z/ (ز), /s/ (ص), /d/ (ض), /t/ (ط), /z/ (ظ), /l/ (ع), /gh/ (غ), /q/ (ق).
- **Igbo:** /th/ (ث), /h/ (ح), /dh/ (ذ), /s/ (ص), /d/ (ض), /t/ (ط), /q/ (ق).

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- **Nupe:** /th/ (ث), /h/ (ح), /kh/ (خ), /z/ (ز), /s/ (ص), /d/ (ض).

Thus, collectively, these tribes converge on **twelve Arabic consonants** that are typically altered into substitute sounds in their native languages. These are:

/th/, /h/, /kh/, /dh/, /z/, /s/, /d/, /t/, /z/, /' /, /gh/, /q/.

The researcher selected these four ethnic groups (Hausa, Yoruba, Igbo, and Nupe) over others in Nigeria because they serve as a representative sample: Hausa in the **North**, Yoruba in the **South**, and Igbo in the **East**.

At this point, it is worth noting those Arabic sounds which the classical Qur'ānic reciters vehemently rejected when mispronounced, as a comparison with the kinds of phonological substitutions that have appeared in the Nigerian Muslim community. These include:

- /k/ pronounced as /j/.
- /j/ pronounced as /sh/.
- /j/ pronounced as /k/.
- /t/ pronounced as /t/.
- /d/ weakened into a light sound.
- /s/ pronounced as /s/.
- /z/ pronounced as /t/.
- /f/ pronounced as /b/.

Comparison of Original Arabic Sounds with Their Altered Forms

When comparing the original Arabic sounds with those that have been altered—either into colloquial Arabic variants among Arabs themselves, or into foreign substitutions in some Nigerian languages—the following table becomes evident:

Original Letter	Colloquial Altered Form	Colloquial Altered Form
/th/ (ث)	None	cha (Hausa) / sa (Yoruba)
/h/ (ح)	None	ha (Hausa) / a (Yoruba)
	None	ha (Hausa) / a (Yoruba)
/dh/ (ذ)	None	zali (Hausa) / sali (Yoruba)
/z/ (ز)	None	za (Hausa) / sa (Yoruba)
/s/ (ص)	Pronounced as /s/	sadi (Hausa) / sodi (Yoruba)
/d/ (ض)	Weakened “light” dād	rodi (Hausa) / lodi (Yoruba)
/t/ (ط)	Pronounced as /t/	da (Hausa) / taa (Yoruba)
/z/ (ظ)	Pronounced as /t/	za (Hausa) / sa (Yoruba)
/' (ع)	None	an (Hausa) / am (Yoruba)
/gh/ (غ)	None	ga (Hausa) / gan (Yoruba)
/q/ (ق)	None	ka (Hausa) / ka (Yoruba)

From the table, it is clear that the colloquial alterations (اللحن العامي) which are rejected in Qur'ānic recitation intersect with the foreign substitutions in **four letters**:

- /t/ (ط) → pronounced as /t/.
- /d/ (ض) → weakened form.
- /s/ (ص) → pronounced as /s/.
- /z/ (ظ) → pronounced as /t/.

To these, we may also add /f/ (ف) pronounced as /b/, which, although not listed in the table, occurs specifically in Hausa, in the other hand letter /m/ (م) which is pronounced by Lagosians in the south in a different sound as /mo/

Thus, just as it is impermissible to recite with these **eight colloquial forms**, it is likewise unacceptable to recite with their corresponding **foreign substitutes**, since both alter the intended sound and performance of the Qur'ān

Phonological solecism in the Recitation of al-Fātiḥah Among Nigerian Tribes

The text of Sūrat al-Fātiḥah is as follows:

"الحمد لله رب العالمين.....الخ"

The points of legitimate difference in its recitation (qirā'āt) are limited to two locations only:

1. In the phrase “**Māliki yawmi al-dīn**” (مَالِكِ يَوْمِ الدِّينِ):
 - 'Āṣim and al-Kisā'ī recited it with consonant alif after mim (**Māliki**).
 - The remaining reciters read it without alif (**Maliki**).
2. In the phrase “**al-sirāṭ / al-sirāṭ**” (الصِّرَاطِ / السِّرَاطِ):
 - Ibn Kathīr, in the narration of al-Qawwās, recited it with **sīn** (al-sirāṭ).

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○ The rest recited it with **ṣād** (al-ṣirāt).

Beyond these two variations, no other differences exist in the authentic recitational traditions, except in minor aspects of tartīl (intonation and grammatical pauses).

Al-Fātiḥah and Its Phonological Problems in Nigeria

Before addressing the widespread phonological difficulties that Nigerian Muslims encounter in reciting al-Fātiḥah, it is important to highlight a **distorted form of its recitation** that emerged among some traditionalist scholars. This form has been propagated in certain communities, particularly among the so-called “hallway scholars” (al-‘ulamā’ al-dahlīziyīn) in the southern part of Nigeria. In their ideological perspective, the form of the Fatiḥah came is referred in a foreignized caption as: “**Al-barkalize Fātiḥah**” meaning “the Blessed Fatiḥah”

This phrasing, however, is a **serious distortion of the origin text of Qur’ān**, and nothing less than a misrepresentation of the Book of Allah. The text of this so-called “vernacular recitation” is as follows:

Arabic Transcription of the phrasing

فَاتِحَ الْبَرَكَا – أَلْأَمْدُ لِلَّهِ رَبِّ الْعَالَمِينَ – أَرَامَانَ الرَّبِّ
 مَلِكِ يَوْمِ الدِّينِ – إِيَّاكَ نَسْتَعِينُ – وَإِيَّاكَ نَسْتَعِينُ
 إِدْنَا سِرَاتِ الْمُسْتَقِيمِ – سِرَاتِ الَّذِينَ أَنْعَمْتَ عَلَيْهِمْ –
 غَيْرِ الْمَغْلُوبِ عَلَيْهِمْ وَلَا الْإِلَّيْنِ – آمِي

Transliteration

Fātiḥah	Alubarika	–	Al-’amudu	lillā’i	rabi	li-’ālamīna	–	Ar-ramāni	r-raḥīmi	–
Maliki	yaumi	-dīni	–	’Iyāka	na’abudu	–	wa-’iyāka	nas’ta’īnu	–	
Ihdinā	ṣirāṭa	l-mustaḥīma	–	ṣirāṭa	l-ladhīna	an’amta	’alayhimu	–		

ghayri li-maghalūbi ‘alayhimu walā ḍ-ḍālīna – Āmīn

A number of Muslims in **Southern Nigeria**, particularly in the **Emirate of Ilorin**, firmly believed that reciting al-Fātiḥah in this distorted manner would bring blessing (baraka) upon whatever it was recited over. For this reason, it came to be called “**Fātiḥat al-Baraka**” (the Opening of Blessing). This mispronounced form of recitation became widespread in the **1970s**, marking a specific period in the religious history of this Emirate. The researcher continues to investigate this phenomenon carefully, seeking to determine:

- **its origin,**
- **whether any authentic form of it ever existed,**
- **the precise method and style in which it was introduced,**
- **and the authority or group responsible for its spread.**

What is clear, however, is that the belief in its supposed blessing has extended its harmful influence across the entirety of Southern Nigeria.

Al-Fātiḥah and its Phonological Challenges in Nigeria

The following version of Sūrat al-Fātiḥah represents a common phonological distortion found among several Nigerian Muslim communities:

(الأمد لله رب العالمين – الرأمن الربيم – ملك يوم الدين – إياك نأبد وإياك نستعين – إدنا سرات المستقيم – سرات الذين أنأمت عليهم غير المغدوب أو المغدوب عليهم ولا الدالين أو اللالين)

Transliteration

al-’amdu lillāhi rabb al-’ālamīn – ar-ra’man ar-ra’im – malik yawm ad-dīn – iyyāka na’bud wa-iyyāka nasta’in – idna sarāt al-mustaḥīm – sarāt alladhīna an’amta ‘alayhim ghayr al-maghdūb (or al-maghlūb, or al-magdūb) ‘alayhim wa-lā ad-dālīn (or al-lālīn). It is evident that the consonant /d/ (ض) is the most frequently altered among the substituted phonemes in the above rendering. The reason may be attributed to the fact that the /d/ is one of the most acoustically complex and phonetically marked sounds in the Arabic language. The Prophet Muḥammad (peace be upon him) is reported to have said in a well-known narration: “I am the most eloquent in pronouncing the ḍād.” Thus, the classical Arab phoneticians devoted considerable attention to the study and analysis of this phoneme. According to **Sībawayh** and **Ibn al-Jazarī**, the /d/ shares certain articulatory features with the /l/ due to their proximity in the oral cavity.

Sībawayh describes the articulation of /d/ as:

“From between the side of the tongue and the molars is the point of articulation of the ḍād. From the side of the tongue, extending to its tip, against what lies opposite in the upper palate—above the canine, premolars, and incisors—lies the articulation of the lām.” (Al-Qanbari, V.2 p409)

Ibn al-Jazarī poetically summarizes this in his Muqaddimah al-Jazariyyah:

.....**والضاد من حافته إذ وليا .
 لاضراس من أيسر أو يمناها** واللام أناها لمنتهاها

Translation

“The *dād* originates from the side of the tongue when it comes into contact with the molars, whether from the left side or the right. The *lām* emerges closer to the tip, extending to its furthest point.” This highlights both the **difficulty** and the **distinctiveness** of the Arabic /d/, which often leads to its substitution by /d/, /l/, or /r/ in Nigerian recitation in the mid-7th and 8th centuries AH, Ibn al-Jazarī continued to draw attention to certain manifestations of change and distortion in the pronunciation of the /dād/ during his time. He noted cases of confusion between /dād/ and other sounds such as /zāʾ/, /dhāl/, /zāy/, and a heavy /lām/, though he did not specify the exact places or communities where this confusion occurred.

It is evident, however, that the articulation points of these five sounds are not identical. Ibn Jinnī describes them as follows: the /dād/ emerges from the side of the tongue and the adjoining molars; /zāʾ/ and /dhāl/ originate between the tongue and the tips of the incisors; while /zāy/ comes from the contact between the incisors and the tongue tip.

Ibn al-Jazarī strongly rejected this confusion, stating: “This is impermissible in the recitation of the Book of Allah, as it alters the intended meaning. For instance, if we were to say **al-ḡāllīm** with a /z/, it would mean ‘the perpetual ones,’ which contradicts the intended meaning of Allah Almighty and invalidates the prayer.” (Al-jazari, p.130-131)

Al-Safāqīsī also commented on this phenomenon, observing that some reciters transformed the Qurʾānic /dād/ into the lingual /dhāl/, particularly when /dhāl/ occurred adjacent to one of the seven emphatic sounds (qāf, zāʾ, khāʾ, ṣād, dād, ghayn, tāʾ). He classified this as a clear and major error (laḥn fāḥish jalī). His warning came in the context of his broader notes on common mistakes and phonetic “diseases” affecting Qurʾānic recitation. (Al-sofaqīsī, p.58)

On this basis, the sounds /ʾayn/, /ḥāʾ/, /ṣād/, and /dād/—which do not exist in the consonant inventories of the major Nigerian languages—are systematically substituted with phonetically proximate alternatives during recitation. For example, /ʾ/ and /ḥ/ are produced from the middle of the pharynx, while /ṣ/ emerges from the contact of the tongue tip with the incisors, and /dād/—as discussed earlier—originates from the side of the tongue and the molars.

This phonological tendency has had a profoundly negative effect on the recitation of Sūrat al-Fātiḥah among these communities. Such alterations are particularly troubling, as al-Fātiḥah is the essential pillar of worship, and no prayer is valid without it.

The words (al-ḥamdu), (al-Raḥmān), and (al-Raḥīm) are often pronounced by many Nigerian worshippers as (al-amdu), (al-raʾman), and (al-raʾīm) respectively. According to the phonological study conducted by Deremi Abubakr, this difficulty of pronunciation can be attributed to the phenomenon of **phonetic contraction** among Yoruba speakers of Arabic. (Deremi, p.90-91)

The form (al-amdu) is derived from *amad* (meaning “time” or “duration”), as in Allah’s saying: “*amad-an baʾidā*” (“a distant span of time”). The word (al-raʾman), however, has no corresponding meaning in Arabic, whereas (al-raʾīm) is an anomalous form of the adjective pattern *faʾīl*, derived from *raʾm* (to show deep affection). The expected form is *raʾūm*, which denotes the tender love of a compassionate mother for her child, akin to *raʾūf* (compassionate, merciful). Thus, *raʾīm* is an irregular and unfamiliar form in Arabic usage.

Furthermore, the consonant /ʾ/ in words such as (al-ʾālamīn), (naʾbudu), (nastaʾīn), and (anʾamta) is replaced with a glottal stop /ʔ/, yielding pronunciations such as (al-ʾālamīn), (naʾbud), (nastaʾīn), and (anʾamta).

Alpha Fofana, a specialist in contemporary linguistics, explains that this substitution reflects the phenomenon of **ʾanʾana**, historically associated with the tribe of Tamīm, in which the hamza /ʾ/ is substituted for ʾayn /ʾ/. For instance, the word (innaka) (“indeed you”) would be pronounced (ʾinnaka). (Fofana, p.44)

This substitution is facilitated by the close articulatory proximity of the two sounds: the /ʾ/ is pharyngeal, while the /ʔ/ is glottal. However, replacing hamza with ʾayn, or vice versa, or with /h/, significantly alters the meaning of words, since /ʔ/, /ʾ/, and /h/ are each distinct phonemes in Arabic.

Some linguists have acknowledged the phenomenon of phonemic substitution in phonological studies. ʾAbd al-Tawwāb, for example, explains the linguistic cause for replacing one sound with another: “The sound hamza is extremely difficult to articulate, since its pronunciation requires the compression of air behind the vocal cords, followed by a sudden release. This process demands considerable muscular effort, and some tribes—particularly those of the Ḥijāz—attempted to avoid it. (Ramadhan, p.12-13)

However, Ramaḍān’s recognition of this phenomenon does not contradict the reality that substitution often leads to semantic distortion. He himself noted: “Such substitutions result in corruption of meaning.” Similarly, Fofana observed that “substitution may alter the meaning of a word, since hamza /ʔ/, ʾayn /ʾ/, and hāʾ /h/ are independent phonemes in Arabic.

Accordingly, it is evident that words in which certain consonants of these sacred Qurʾānic texts are substituted undergo significant semantic alteration. For instance:

- (al-ʾālamīn) [as pronounced in Nigeria] becomes the plural of *ālim* (one who suffers pain), derived from *ʾalima yaʾlamu* (“to feel pain”), rather than “all worlds. (Ibn Manzur, p.68)
- (naʾbud) is derived from *ʾabada bi-l-makān* (“to remain permanently in a place”), or from *taʾabbada* (“to become wild, untamed”), instead of “we worship. (Ibn Manzur, p.567)
- (nastaʾīn) is meaningless within Arabic vocabulary.
- (anʾamta) is derived from *naʾma* (“a faint hidden sound”) or from *naʾmat al-asad* (“the low growl of a lion”), instead of “You bestowed [favor]. (Ibn Manzur, p.637)

Phonological Challenges in the Recitation of Al-Fātiḥah among Nigerian Muslims

Moreover, due to frequent usage, haste in recitation, and hyper articulation (phonetic contraction), the phoneme /h/ in (ihdinā) is often dropped, resulting in (idnā). Similarly, the word (al-ṣirāt) is distorted when the ṣād /s/ is replaced with sīn /s/, and among Yoruba speakers the tā' /t/ is often replaced by tā' /t/, producing (sirāt). Although the reading with sīn (sirāt) is attested in valid canonical recitations, in this Nigerian context it is not deliberate but rather a mistake and a distortion.

Additionally, in Hausa phonology, the consonant /d/ approximates the Arabic tā' /t/. As a result, Hausa speakers tend to substitute this sound in (al-ṣirāt), sometimes producing a variant close to /d/ instead of the correct tā'.

The sound /d/ (dād) has undergone deviation, being pronounced sometimes as /d/, sometimes as /l/, and at other times as /r/. Thus, the words (al-maghdūb) and (al-dāllīn) are rendered in these distorted forms: (al-maghdūb / al-maghlūb), (ad-dāllīn), (ar-rāllīn), and (al-lāllīn).

Phonetically, /d/ is a voiced, emphatic dental-palatal sound, corresponding to /d/—which is also dental, though non-emphatic. In contrast, /l/ and /r/ are alveolar sounds, with /r/ being a trill. All of these consonants, however, are voiced.

Among Nigerian worshippers, it is particularly noticeable that this phonological difficulty with /d/ manifests in frequent substitution by /d/ or /l/ when followed by the rounded vowel /u/, and by /d/ or /r/ when preceded by the open vowel /a/. This is unsurprising, for long vowels and consonants are phonological elements that pose significant challenges to Nigerian speakers of Arabic.

To clarify further:

- The distorted form (al-maghdūb), instead of (al-maghdūb), derives from the root ghadaba–yaghdbu meaning “a thick flesh-like substance,” whence rajul ghadb: “a course, harsh man.”
- (al-maghlūb), on the other hand, comes from ghalaba–yaghlibu (“to overpower”), with maghlūb meaning “the one who is defeated.”
- (ad-dāllīn) is the plural of dāll (active participle from dalla–yadullu “to guide, indicate”), as in the ḥadīth of Anas ibn Mālik (may Allah be pleased with him): “The one who points (ad-dāll) to good is like the one who performs it.”

Regrettably, the outcome of these substitutions within the words of Sūrat al-Fātiḥah—caused by phonological challenges—has been a profound negative distortion of meanings and contexts. Thus, for instance, the noble word (al-ḥamdu), which was revealed to signify praise and glorification, becomes a word implying censure. Similarly, the verb (na'bud), which embodies the servant's devotion to his Lord, is transformed into an expression of avoidance or estrangement from Him—and so fort.

CONCLUSION

After a careful and thorough investigation, the researcher has determined that a large number of worshippers in Nigeria commit grave linguistic errors due to the phonological challenges they face in pronouncing certain Arabic consonants. They frequently substitute these sounds with those closest to them in their own local languages.

It is clear that the Arabic consonants most difficult for Muslims of this region to articulate correctly are: /t/ (ث), /h/ (ح), /ḥ/ (خ), /' / (ع), /d/ (د), /z/ (ذ), /h/ (ه), /s/ (ص), /d/ (ض), /d/ (possibly a typo repetition), /k/ (ك), /q/ (ق), /t/ (ط), and /z/ (ظ). These are pharyngeal, emphatic, and interdental consonants.

It is certain that learners of Arabic in Nigeria encounter particular difficulty with **interdental consonants** (such as /ظ/, /ذ/, /ث/), some **pharyngeal consonants** (such as /ع/, /ح/), and the **emphatic consonants** (such as /ظ/, /ط/, /ض/, /ص/).

On the other hand, both the Hausa and Yoruba speakers do not face serious difficulties with the **Arabic vowels (ḥarakāt)**, as these already exist in their native languages.

Therefore, the researcher has taken the Hausa and Yoruba ethnic groups as representative models for the Muslim tribes of Nigeria—since it is from these two groups that most of the other tribes have received their knowledge of religion and cultural education.

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